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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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A CONCEPTUAL DISCOURSE ON PROTECTING THE RIGHTS OF ELECTRONIC COMMERCE CONSUMERS IN NIGERIA*

By
Muhammad Nuruddeen**

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this paper is to conduct a conceptual discourse on issues relating to protecting the rights of electronic commerce consumers (e-consumers) in Nigeria. The paper raises a question as to who shall bear the responsibility of protecting the rights of consumers: Is it the consumer himself? The government? The suppliers? Or the society as a whole? In an effort to respond to this question, the paper adopts a doctrinal research methodology. Equally, the paper analyses the principle of caveat emptor, free market theory as well as collective responsibility and paternalism ideologies to respond to the question as well. The paper argues that the philosophy behind consumer protection abounds. Consumer protection regime empowers consumers, guards them against exploitation and deceptive practices in the market arena. The paper observes that protecting the rights of e-consumers is a collective responsibility but the bulk of which lies with the government. The paper recommends that Nigeria should update its consumer protection laws. In so doing, the government should ensure that such laws are in line with the relevant international legal instruments identified by this paper.

Keywords: consumerism; paternalism; caveat emptor; free market theory; e-commerce, e-traders and e-consumers

1. INTRODUCTION

The advent of e-commerce has brought into existence a new group of consumers known as e-consumers. The number of e-consumers is rapidly increasing. At the moment, many people take e-commerce as a modern way of life. Protecting the e-consumers has become necessary in view of the complex nature of the technology involved in e-commerce transactions. Besides, the bargaining strength between the e-consumer and the electronic traders (e-traders) is never equal. The e-traders are economically more powerful than the e-consumer. The disparity between the two in terms of knowledge is another source of concern. Many times, the e-traders utilise the magical power of the technology to mislead consumers. This can be done at the point of advertisement, promotions and/or sales. On this premise, the paper carries out a conceptual discourse on issues affecting the rights of the Nigerian consumers generally and e-consumers in particular.

2. THE CONCEPT OF CONSUMER PROTECTION

The term “consumer” is elastic in nature and has no precise meaning.¹ The term can be traced to the Latin word "*consumere*", meaning to consume.² Literally, consumer means, one who purchases goods and services as opposed to a producer.³ The Black's Law Dictionary defined a consumer as a person who buys goods for personal, family or house hold use, with no intention of resale.⁴ Conversely, Adam Smith said that

*This is an updated version of a seminar paper entitled "*Protecting the Rights of Electronic Consumers in Nigeria: A Conceptual Discourse*" which was presented by the author and Reported in the Book of Proceedings of Seminar on Law and Society 2016 (SOLAS 2016), Organised by the School of Law, Universiti Utara Malaysia, held on 6th December, 2016 at College of Law, Government and International Studies (COLGIS), Universiti Utara Malaysia, Sintok, Kedah, Malaysia.

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¹ Onwanyi Ulegede, "Liability Regime and Consumer Issues in Road Transfort," in *Law and Principles of Consumer Protection*, ed. Adedeji Adekunle and Shankyula Tersoo Samuel (Lagos, Nigeria: Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 2013), 418–449, at pp. 420-21; Joseph Jar Kur, "Quality Control in Modern Trademark Licencing: A Call for Greater Protection of Consumers in the 21st Century," in *Law and Principles of Consumer Protection*, ed. Adedeji Adekunle and Shankyula Tersoo Samuel (Lagos, Nigeria: Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 2013), 450–478, at p. 450.

² A. D. Badaiki, "Effect of Privatisation and Commercialisation Policy on Consumer Protection in Nigeria," in *Law and Principles of Consumer Protection*, ed. Adedeji Adekunle and Shankyula Tersoo Samuel (Lagos, Nigeria: Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 2013), 146–213, at pp. 155-158.

³ A. S. Hornby, *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English* (London: Oxford University Press, 1974); Felicia Nwanne Monye, "Tips on Consumer Protection," *Consumer Journal* 2, no. 1 (2006): 145–158, at p. 145.

⁴ Kur J. J., op cit., at p. 450.

consumer covers individuals, families and firms.⁵ Similarly, it is argued that a consumer can be a person and an organisation as well.⁶ In other words, the definition of a consumer is not only limited to natural persons.

In the same vein, the term is not restricted to direct buyers of goods or services. It is extended to any person who is affected by such goods or services. Badaiki argued that a consumer includes those who use, maintain. or dispose of products as opposed to direct buyers.⁷ In the words of Akwueze, a consumer is any person who uses or is affected by goods or services.⁸ In *Donoghue v. Stevenson*,⁹ Lord Atkin, referred to a consumer as “persons who are so closely and directly affected by my acts...”¹⁰ Therefore, any person who is affected by goods or services can answer the name of a consumer no matter how remote.

A class or group of individuals also fall within the meaning of a consumer. This position is favoured by Monye *et al.* in their reaction to the definition offered by the Consumer Protection Council Act 1992. The Act defines a consumer as an individual who purchases, uses, maintains or disposes of goods or services.¹¹ In the circumstance, Monye *et al.* opined that the use of the word “individual” in the Act did not bar an action by a group or class of individuals.¹² Thus, a class or group of individuals is entitled to all rights guaranteed to an individual consumer under the Act.

Recently, any person who engages in e-commerce transactions is also added to the group of consumers (e-consumer). According to Naemah and Roshazlizwati, an e-consumer is purchaser of goods and services over electronic systems such as the

⁵ Adam Smith, *An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*, ed. R.H. Campbell, A.S. Skinner, and W.B. Todd (Indianapolis: Liberty Classic, 1981).

⁶ L. G. Schiffman and L. L. Kanut, *Consumer Behaviour* (Eaglewood Cliffs: Prentice-Hall, 1978) pp. 4-5.

⁷ Badaiki, A. D., *op cit.*

⁸ F.O. Akwueze, “Legal Challenges of Obtaining Consumer Redress in Nigeria,” *Journal of Contemporary Law* 1 (2012): 116.

⁹ AC, *Donoghue v Stevenson* 562 (1932).

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ CPC Act has now been repealed by Section 165 of the *Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission Act, 2018* which also defined a consumer to “include any person who purchases or offers to purchase goods otherwise than for the purpose of resale...” See also Nuruddeen Muhammad, “Access to Justice by Electronic Commerce Consumers (E-consumers) through the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission” *NIALS Journal of Business Law, Vol. 4* (2021): 148-182. Janet M. Asagh, “Consumer Protection and Telecommunications Services in Nigeria: Regulatory and Policy Issues,” in *Law and Principles of Consumer Protection*, ed., Adedeji Adekunle and Shankyula Tersoo Samuel (Lagos, Nigeria: Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 2013), 277–298, at p. 279.

¹² Felicia Monye, Boniface Umoh, and Chinyere Chukwunta, *Research Report on the State of Consumer Protection In Nigeria : Review of Consumer Protection in the Telecommunications Sector in Nigeria* (Nigeria: Consumer Awareness Organisation, 2014), 1-194.

Internet.¹³ Today, e-consumers are increasing as e-commerce becomes a modern lifestyle.¹⁴ E-consumers can be individuals, groups or institutions just like the ordinary consumers.

2.1 MEANING OF CONSUMER PROTECTION

The phrase “consumer protection” does not have a precise meaning. Thus, consumer protection refers to legislation which protects the Interest of consumers.¹⁵ Also, consumer protection means safeguarding the interests of the consumer.¹⁶ The consumer protection regime is aimed at reducing or preventing wrongs occasioned by consumers in the course of commerce.¹⁷ Equally, the regime identifies those rights accorded to the consumer as well as enables him enjoy the rights.¹⁸

2.2 CONSUMER RIGHTS

As pointed above, a consumer protection regime identifies those rights accorded to consumers. In 1962, the US President, John F. Kennedy identified the four basic rights of the consumer.¹⁹ They are, the right to choice, information, safety and the right to be heard. In 1985, the UN came up with the Guidelines for Consumer Protection which introduced four new rights, alongside the said four basic rights.²⁰ These rights are incorporated *mutatis mutandis* into other international legal instruments and municipal laws of many countries.²¹ These rights keep on evolving as the society changes.²² For instance, with the advent of e-commerce, new rights for consumers

¹³ Naemah and Roshazlizwati, *op cit*.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*; Gyanendra M. Fulzalke and V. M. More, “Amplified Abstract on the Consumer and Contract Terms,” in *University of Pretoria International Consumer Law Conference* (Pretoria: Faculty of Law, University of Pretoria, 2016).

¹⁵ R. Bird, *Osborn’s Concise Law Dictionary*, 7th ed. (London: Sweet and Maxwell, 1983) at p. 90.

¹⁶ Felicia Monye, *Law of Consumer Protection* (Ibadan, Nigeria: Spectrum Books Ltd., 2003), at p. 20.

¹⁷ B.B. Kanyip, *Consumer Protection in Nigeria: Law, Theory & Policy* (Abuja, Nigeria: Reckon Books Ltd, 2005), at p. 27.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ Kamarudeen Babatunde Bello, Jamila Bisi Aduke Suleiman, and Ibrahim Danjuma, “Perspectives on Consumerism and Consumer Protection Act in Nigeria,” *European Journal of Business and Management* 4, no. 10 (2012): 72–79.

²⁰ Kur, J. J., *op cit.*, at pp. 461-463.

²¹ Anthony .A. Ijewere and Stephen O Obeki, “Consumerism in Nigeria,” *JORIND* 9, no. 2 (2011): 186–192, at 187.

²² Brown Robin, Charley Lewis, and Jeremy Malcolm, “Foundation For Effective Markets & Governance, LINK Centre of Wits University, and Consumers International,” in *Updating the United Nations Guidelines for Consumer Protection for Digital Age*, ed. Jeremy Malcolm (Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia: Consumer International, 2013), 1–113, at p. 8.

emerged. E-consumers now have digital data protection and privacy rights.²³ The right to delivery of physical or intangible goods. But more importantly, the right to accurate information about online goods and services.²⁴ In fact, the right to information is undoubtedly the most fundamental consumer right.²⁵ Thus, the right to information is paramount both in online and offline transactions.

3. WHO HAS THE DUTY TO PROTECT CONSUMER RIGHTS?

There seems to be divergent views as to who shall be responsible for ensuring that consumer rights are protected. The views are supported with principles of law, theories, and philosophical ideologies.

3.1 The Principle of *Caveat Emptor* and Free Market Theory

The consumer is the best protector of himself. This is founded upon the principle of *caveat emptor* (let buyer beware).²⁶ The principle presumes that the consumer knows what he wants and has knowledge necessary to choose wisely.²⁷ Thus, he has a prudent mind for making rational decisions²⁸ and shall be accountable for whatever he chooses for himself.²⁹ Provided that no information relating to a product is withheld by the producer.³⁰ Similarly, advocates of free market theory argued that consumer protection is most effectively achieved by the operation of free and open markets.³¹ On the contrary, it was argued that *caveat emptor* principle or free market theory only provide minimal protection for consumers.³² In fact, it was submitted that the *caveat emptor* is no longer a protective measure for consumers.³³ It benefits the producers

²³ Meirong Guo, "A Comparative Study on Consumer Right to Privacy in E-Commerce," *SciRes* 3 (2012): 402–407.

²⁴ Guilherme Varella and Mariana Valente, "Brazilian Consumer Defense Institute (Idec)," in *Updating the United Nations Guidelines for Consumer Protection for Digital Age*, ed. Jeremy Malcolm (Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia: Consumer International, 2013), 1–113, at p. 78.; Roshazlizawati Mohd Nor and Naemah Amin, "E-Consumer Protection in Delivery of Goods: A Malaysian Perspective," *Journal of Education and Social Sciences* 3 (Feb.) (2016): 38–44.

²⁵ Jules Stuyck, "European Consumer Law after the Treaty of Amsterdam: Consumer Policy in or Beyond the Internal Market?," *CML.Rev* (2000): 270, 420.

²⁶ Kamarudeen, B.B., *et al.*, op cit., at p. 76.

²⁷ Ndubisi, E.C., *et al.*, at p. 530.

²⁸ M.J. Trebilcock, "Consumer Protection in the Affluent Society," *McGill Law Journal* 16 (1971): 263.

²⁹ Umar Al-Mustapha Machido and A. A. Akume, "An Evaluation of Product Liability Law: Its Benefit and Costs," in *Law and Principles of Consumer Protection*, ed. Adedaj Adekunle and Shankyula Tersoo Samuel (Lagos, Nigeria: Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 2013), 124–145, at pp. 125-126.

³⁰ Trebilcock, M.J., op cit.

³¹ Peter Cartwright, *Consumer Protection and the Criminal Law: Law, Theory, and Policy in the UK*, 1st ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001), at p. 1.

³² Naemah Amin and Roshazlizawati Mohd, "Online Shopping in Malaysia : Legal Protection for E-Consumers," *European Journal of Business and Management* 5, no. 24 (2013): 79–87, at p. 82.

³³ Ndubisi, E.C., *et al.*, op cit., at p. 529.

more. It gives them the liberty to do as they desire at the expense of the consumer.³⁴ Hence, the need for a better protective measure for consumers.

3.2 Producers Versus Information Disclosure Philosophy

The producers are under obligation to protect the consumers. The consumer can best be protected with an adequate information about products or services offered for sale. The producers are to provide the necessary information that will enable a consumer to make an informed buying decision. In fact, information disclosure philosophy posits that the consumer is entitled to be given all the information they need to make the right choice.³⁵ Information disclosure applies to pre and post sales, including level of advertisements.³⁶ Unfortunately, this argument does not seem to hold water. Because producers do not care about providing the necessary information to consumers. They are just after maximising their profit at the expense of the consumers.

3.3 Collective Responsibility Ideology

Consumer protection is the responsibility of the businesses, the governments and Non-governmental Organisations (NGOs).³⁷ For obvious reasons, consumer protection is the responsibility of all. Because any harm to a consumer as a result of unfair trade practices is a threat to the entire public.³⁸ Without the consumers, there can be no basis for production and hence no market.³⁹ If consumers are not protected, there would not be any sustainable economic development. Also, there would not be any economic productivity and quality standards of goods and services.⁴⁰ Hence, the market would fail and everybody will suffer.

3.4 The Paternalism Ideology

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ P. Edoreh, "Marketing in Nigeria: Principles, Concepts, and Decisions," ed. et al Agbonifoh, 2nd ed. (Aba, Nigeria: Afritowers Ltd., 2007), 33–35.

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Ify Umenyi, "The Role of the Consumer Protection Council in a Liberalised Economy," *Consumer Journal* 2, no. 1 (2006): 68–85, at p. 70.

³⁸ Etefia E Ekanem, "Institutional Framework for Consumers Protection in Nigeria," *International Journal of Advanced Legal Studies and Governance* 2, no. 1 (2011): 33–48, at p.34.

³⁹ Kamarudeen, B.B., *et al.*, *op cit.*, at pp. 72-79.

⁴⁰ Ify, U., *OP CIT.*, at p. 70.

The government has a major role to play in protecting consumers.⁴¹ The consumer would be better protected by the government.⁴² Thus, the bulk of consumer protection lies with the government.⁴³ This is common to most developing countries like Nigeria. Where consumer protection has been more about regulation than support from NGOs. Paternalistic ideology postulates that laws must be made to protect interests of consumers as vulnerable members of the society. The government intervenes in advancing consumer issues through legislation and creation of consumer regulatory agencies. Therefore, consumer protection is a regime of laws and institutions designed to safeguard consumers against exploitations.⁴⁴

4. THE PHILOSOPHY BEHIND CONSUMER PROTECTION

There are a number of reasons for consumer protection in a given society. In Nigeria, several factors necessitate the government to intervene in consumer related matters.⁴⁵ Consumers are continuously sold substandard products and services.⁴⁶ Suppliers manipulate prices, mislead consumers through advertisements and sales promotions. They take advantage of ignorance of consumers to perpetuate these acts.⁴⁷ This makes it imperative for the government to come and assist the consumers.

Vulnerability to exploitation is the foremost ground for consumer protection. There exists inequality of bargaining power between the suppliers and consumers. The same goes for the disparity in terms of knowledge and economic strength.⁴⁸ The inequality in economic strength for instance, manifests in difficulty encountered by the consumer in obtaining redress against the suppliers.⁴⁹ Especially nowadays where cost of litigation is very high.⁵⁰ The inequality in bargaining power also manifests in the insertion of unfair trade terms that mostly favour the suppliers.⁵¹ Therefore, the

⁴¹ Ndubisi, E.C., *et al.*, *op cit.*

⁴² Mark J. Green, "Appropriateness and Responsiveness: Can the Government Protect the Consumer," *Journal of Economic Issues* 8, no. 2 (1974): 309–328.

⁴³ Bello *et al.* *op cit.*, at p. 73.

⁴⁴ Machido, U. and Akume, A.A., *op cit.*

⁴⁵ Kur, J.J., *op cit.*, at p. 452.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ F. O. Ukwueze, "Protection of Consumers of Financial Services in Nigeria: A Review," *Consumer Journal* 2, no. 1 (2006): 108–144, at p. 109.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

⁵⁰ Kur, J. J., *op cit.*, at 461.

⁵¹ Kamarudeen, B.B., *et al.*, *op cit.*, at pp. 72-79.

excesses and exploitations of the suppliers still underscores the justification for consumer protection.

Challenges posed by the advancement of the information technology constitute another justification for consumer protection.⁵² In fact, consumers need protection now more than ever.⁵³ Goods and services are now offered for sale online.⁵⁴ Goods offered online are not capable of being seen or touched physically. Online sales or e-commerce is a complex area where even the most enlightened consumers find it difficult to understand or utilise.⁵⁵ Here, the gap in terms of knowledge and power between consumers and suppliers is even greater.⁵⁶ In view of this, many Nigerians still treat e-commerce with deep scepticism. Thus, protecting the consumers on the cyberspace through relevant legislation has become paramount. It is therefore recommended that Nigeria should update its consumers laws to meet the current international standards. This paper suggests the domestication of, *inter alia*, the UN Guidelines on consumer protection and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Guidelines for Consumer Protection in the Context of Electronic Commerce 1999 in Nigeria. This will certainly help in arresting a lot of problems facing consumers generally and e-consumers in particular.

5. CONCLUSION

A consumer is a key to any business and protecting his rights is paramount. Without the consumer there cannot be any sustainable economic development. Consumers are subjected to all sorts of fraudulent practices, and exploitation with a view to maximising profit. With the advent of e-commerce, consumers need protection now more than ever. In e-commerce, consumers deal with suppliers as well as goods they cannot see physically. E-commerce is very complex and tendencies of fraud and exploitations are very high. Thus, after exploring the principle of *caveat emptor*, free market theory, collective responsibility, and paternalism ideologies, this paper came to a conclusion that protecting e-consumers is a collective responsibility. But the

⁵² Kur, J. J., op cit., at 461-62.

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Oguche, S., op cit., at p. 269.

⁵⁶ Kur, J. J., op cit., at pp. 461-462.

government has a greater responsibility in that respect, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. The paper recommends that Nigeria should update its consumer protection laws. In so doing, the government should align the laws with the relevant international legal instruments identified by this paper.